

Modelling and Parameter Estimation of Propylene Polymerisation Reactor: Industrial Case Study

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ABSTRACT

Parameter estimation in complex industrial process models is hampered by many unknown parameters and limited measurement informativeness. A first-principles DAE model of an industrial fluidised-bed propylene polymerisation reactor (Slovnaft, a.s.) is developed and validated. Combining local and global sensitivity analysis with orthogonalisation, 8 out of 59 parameters are found estimable. A nonlinear least-squares identification on 1 000 industrial data points yields a model that accurately predicts concentrations and temperature across all operating conditions.

MOTIVATION & OBJECTIVES

First-principles modelling is a cornerstone of chemical process engineering – yet it is challenged by:

- High model structure complexity
- Many unknown parameters
- Parameter interdependence (non-identifiability)
- Limited measurement quality and informativeness

This work addresses the systematic identification of estimable parameters for an industrial fluidised-bed propylene polymerisation reactor – bridging rigorous process modelling with real plant data.

Objectives:

1. Develop a first-principles DAE reactor model
2. Perform sensitivity & estimability analysis
3. Identify the estimable subset
4. Model validation on industrial data

PROCESS DESCRIPTION

- Ziegler–Natta catalyst (TiCl₃ / TEAL co-catalyst)
- Constant-bubble-size fluidised-bed model
- Heat & mass balances, kinetics, thermodynamics, hydrodynamics
- Method of moments for chain-length distribution

MODEL STRUCTURE

The reactor model is a set of differential-algebraic equations (DAEs):

Total parameters: $N_\theta = 59$

Measured outputs ($N_y = 7$): concentrations (C₃H₆, H₂, N₂), bed temperature T , melt flow index, production rate, polymer density.

Simulation tool: DAE solver – ode15s (MATLAB), sampling time $\Delta t = 1$ min

ESTIMABILITY ANALYSIS

A total of 59 parameters are analyzed for predictability. These include kinetic parameters (pre-exponential factors, activation energies) and polymer property parameters. Parameters are ranked using two sensitivity approaches and an orthogonalisation algorithm.

Step 1 – Local Sensitivity Analysis

Perturb one parameter θ_i at a time; obtain dynamics and steady-state; construct the local sensitivity matrix S_L .

Step 2 – Global Sensitivity (Sobol' Indices)

Perturb all parameters simultaneously; obtain dynamics and steady-state; compute Sobol's indices; build S_G .

Step 3 – Orthogonalisation & Ranking

1. Compute the magnitude of each column of S
2. Select the column with the largest magnitude
3. Orthogonalize – regress all remaining columns and compute the residual matrix R
4. Repeat steps 2-3 on R to select the next most influential parameter
5. Stop when the largest residual column magnitude drops below a cut-off threshold $\theta = 0.04$

Only 8 out of 59 parameters are estimable from the available measurements.

PARAMETER IDENTIFICATION

The values of the estimable parameter vector $p \in \mathbb{R}^{N_p} \subset \theta \in \mathbb{R}^{N_\theta}$ is found by solving:

$$\min_p \sum_{t=1}^{\varphi} \|y(t) - f(x(t), \theta)\|_W^2$$

where W is a diagonal weight matrix (inverse measurement variance) of measured y and predicted f outputs.

Dataset:

- $\varphi = 1\,000$ industrial measurements
- Savitzky–Golay pre-filter (order 3, window 9 min)
- Standardised: zero initial value, unit standard deviation

Solver Strategy:

- Nonlinear least-squares (Levenberg–Marquardt)
- Multi-start initialisation to escape local minima
- Bounds enforced from physical constraints

Result: $N_p = 8$ parameters identified with tight confidence intervals ($< 15\%$ relative uncertainty).

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RESULTS

Model validation on testing set (7 000 samples):

- Predictions correctly track C₃H₆, H₂, N₂ concentrations and bed temperature T
- Dynamics agree during constant-temperature operation and grade transitions
- Good fit also for production rate, MFI, and density

Variable	Relative RMSE
[C ₃ H ₆]	< 3%
[H ₂]	< 4%
[N ₂]	< 3%
T	< 1 K

CONCLUSIONS

- A first-principles DAE model for an industrial propylene polymerisation fluidised-bed reactor was developed and validated.
- Combined local + global sensitivity analysis with orthogonalisation identified only 8 estimable parameters from 59 candidates.
- The identified model accurately predicts industrial measurements across different operating points and grade transitions.
- The methodology provides a systematic, reproducible framework for parameter estimability in complex polymerisation models.

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